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TEACHING OUTSIDE SPECIALISM: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF ENGLISH TEACHERS IN A PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Dhan Oliver T. CABANTOG¹
Ruth A. ORTEGA-DELA CRUZ²

¹ Department of Education, Division of Laguna, District of Santa Rosa, Malitlit Elementary School, Santa Rosa City, Laguna, Philippines

² Institute for Governance and Rural Development, College of Public Affairs and Development, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Domingo M. Lantican Ave. College, Laguna, Philippines

Abstract

In many education systems, teachers are frequently assigned to teach subjects beyond their area of specialism - a practice that remains underexplored, particularly at the elementary level. This qualitative exploratory case study examined the lived experiences of five English teachers navigating out-of-field teaching assignments. Findings revealed that teacher responses varied based on demographic factors. Older teachers demonstrated greater resilience, drawing on years of experience, while younger teachers faced steeper challenges. Male teachers relied on peer support and professional development, whereas female teachers leaned on self-initiative and digital tools. Teachers with advanced degrees actively sought professional growth, while those with less training expressed interest in further development. The study highlights how teachers adapt to instructional demands despite limited subject expertise, underscoring the need for targeted support. These insights inform teacher deployment, training, and policy—emphasizing the importance of mentorship and flexible learning opportunities to improve teaching quality in under-resourced settings.

Keywords: Teaching outside specialism, Experiences, Challenges, English teachers

1. Introduction

Teaching outside specialism, or out-of-field teaching, refers to the practice of assigning teachers to subjects for which they lack formal academic training or professional preparation (Hobbs et al., 2022; Price et al., 2019). This issue is increasingly common across global education systems, particularly in developing countries like the Philippines. In rural or under-resourced areas, chronic staffing shortages and inflexible deployment policies often force school administrators to assign teachers to subjects beyond their area of expertise—for example, non-English majors teaching English, or Math teachers covering Science (Nesterova & Young, 2020; Peña & Galigao, 2024).

A 2024 report by the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) and the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II) revealed that up to 62% of high school teachers were teaching subjects outside their formal specialization. This widespread mismatch has been linked to a lack of plantilla positions, limited budgets, and improvised district-level staffing decisions (Chi, 2024; EDCOM II, 2025).

While DepEd policies emphasize the importance of subject specialization and workload regulation—for instance, DepEd Order No. 1, s. 2004 (which sets guidelines for the hiring and deployment of Teacher I positions), DepEd Order No. 019, s. 2025 (which strengthens qualification standards in line with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers), and the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (RA 4670), which limits daily classroom teaching to six hours—these frameworks are often difficult to implement in practice. The 2024 rollout of the MATATAG curriculum reaffirmed these standards, but reports from the ground suggest that out-of-field teaching continues to stretch teachers' capacities and contribute to professional stress. Despite policies that recommend teachers be assigned within their area of certification, school-level realities frequently prioritize subject coverage over subject expertise. This highlights an ongoing implementation gap between policy intent and on-the-ground practice.

Furthermore, while out-of-field teaching may address immediate staffing and operational needs, it raises significant concerns regarding teaching effectiveness, instructional quality, and student learning outcomes. Research indicates that teachers assigned to subjects outside their specialism often face reduced confidence, limited pedagogical content knowledge, and heightened stress—factors that can adversely affect both the quality of instruction and student achievement (Abella & De Jesus, 2021; Mizzi, 2021). This practice also runs counter to the goals of key Philippine education reforms, such as the K to 12 and MATATAG curricula, which emphasize subject-matter expertise, learner-centered pedagogy, and the delivery of high-quality, relevant education.

Despite growing recognition of out-of-field teaching in policy discussions and anecdotal reports from educators, a significant research gap remains—particularly within the Philippine context. Existing studies have largely focused on secondary education or STEM-related subjects, with limited exploration of instruction at the elementary level. Furthermore, much of the current literature relies on quantitative data—such as teacher qualifications and student performance—often neglecting the lived experiences of teachers navigating this challenge. There is a noticeable lack of qualitative, context-specific research that examines how non-specialist teachers adapt to teaching assignments outside their area of expertise, particularly in early education, where foundational skills are established. This gap is critical, as the quality of instruction at the elementary level has long-term implications for student learning.

By centering on the voices and experiences of elementary English teachers assigned to teach outside their specialism, this study aims to address this gap. It seeks to provide deeper insights into the personal, professional, and instructional challenges these teachers face, and to inform more responsive policies on teacher deployment, professional development, and educational equity. In doing so, the research contributes to ongoing efforts to meet Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), especially the commitment to ensuring that all learners are taught by qualified and well-supported teachers.

Specifically, this study (i) described the profile of the participants in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, civil status, and years of teaching experience; and (ii) determined the participants' experiences in teaching outside their specialism.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

Sociocultural theory (Vygotsky, 1978) emphasizes the role of social interaction and guidance from "more knowledgeable others" (MKOs) in cognitive development. Central to this is the *Zone of Proximal Development* (ZPD)—the gap between what a learner can do independently and what they can achieve with support. Vygotsky posits that meaningful learning occurs when students engage in tasks within this zone, assisted by teachers, peers, or mentors (Pathan et al., 2018; Mitchell & Myles, 2004). For teachers working outside their specialization, collaboration with MKOs becomes vital to bridge knowledge gaps and support student learning effectively. Meanwhile, the *More Knowledgeable Others* MKOs are individuals with greater expertise who support learners in acquiring new skills or knowledge. Teachers assigned outside their field may rely on MKOs—colleagues, instructional coaches, or content experts—to enhance instructional accuracy and effectiveness, ensuring quality learning experiences despite their limited subject-area background. Furthermore, Bandura's *self-efficacy theory* suggests that individuals' beliefs in their capabilities influence their actions and resilience. For out-of-field teachers, a strong sense of self-efficacy is crucial (Bandura, 1977). It enables them to adapt to unfamiliar content, engage students confidently, and persist through challenges (Tobin et al., 1994; Roberts et al., 2001). Fostering self-efficacy can help these teachers overcome professional uncertainties and deliver meaningful instruction despite their non-specialist status.

These frameworks inform this study's exploration of how elementary English teachers adapt to non-specialist roles, offering insights into both the external supports and internal motivations that shape their teaching practices and professional growth.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

This study used a qualitative exploratory case study design to examine teachers' experiences teaching outside their specialism. Exploratory research, as noted by Stebbins (2001), is suited for topics with limited prior knowledge, allowing for open-ended exploration of challenges and coping strategies without reliance on existing theories. The case study approach, supported by Yin (2003 in Cruz, 2016), enabled an in-depth understanding of the contextual factors influencing these teachers' experiences.

2.2 Research Participants

This study involved five English major teachers from a public elementary school who faced challenges teaching subjects outside their specialism. Participants were selected through purposeful sampling, a common qualitative method for identifying individuals with rich, relevant experience. Selection criteria included: being a public school English major teaching non-English subjects; having encountered and coped with challenges in teaching outside their expertise; being able to share meaningful insights; and willingness to participate in data collection.

2.3 Instrumentation

This study used creative self-expressive storytelling through in-depth, face-to-face semi-structured interviews. Each participant was interviewed individually to address the research objectives. For Objective 1, participants shared personal background details—age, sex, civil status, education, and teaching experience—to provide context for their experiences. The interviews, guided by researcher-prepared questions, explored how participants came to teach outside their specialism, whether by choice or assignment, and their reflections on its challenges and rewards. Personal stories and memorable experiences were collected to deepen understanding. Each interview lasted one to two hours.

2.4 Data Analysis

This study adhered to established interview analysis guidelines to ensure a thorough and unbiased examination of the real-life experiences of English teachers teaching outside their specialism. Thematic analysis, as recommended by Dodgson (2017), was used to identify and interpret meaningful patterns within the data. The analysis followed a systematic process beginning with transcription, where audio recordings were repeatedly reviewed to capture both the substance and style of participants' speech, allowing for a comprehensive understanding. Each response was then examined to ensure it addressed the interview questions, maintaining data accuracy and reliability. Units of meaning were clustered into themes, which were further analyzed to uncover the core issues represented in the data. The researcher then summarized, validated, and refined these themes to build a coherent and holistic account of participants' experiences. Finally, both common and unique themes across interviews were identified, offering insight into shared challenges and individual variations.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

To uphold ethical standards, the researcher followed all relevant ethical and legal guidelines to protect participants' rights. Participation was entirely voluntary, with special care taken to avoid coercion. Informed consent was obtained after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Participants signed consent forms to confirm their agreement. The researcher ensured no physical or psychological harm would result from participation and maintained strict confidentiality by using coded names and password-protected recordings. Anonymity was preserved throughout to safeguard participants' privacy, ensuring the study was conducted responsibly and ethically.

3. Findings and Discussions

Demographic and Professional Profiles of English Teachers

This section examines the demographic and professional backgrounds of the participants to provide context for their experiences teaching outside their specialism. The analysis is grounded in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, which highlights how social and cultural factors influence learning and professional development. Individual circumstances—such as age, sex, education, and civil status—shape how teachers adapt to new roles and interact within their school environments.

The study involved five English-major public-school teachers, aged 27 to 40. Four participants are single, while one is married. All are currently teaching subjects outside their specialization due to a lack of available positions at the secondary level. Financial incentives and the availability of teaching posts in public schools were key factors influencing their decisions. Three participants are pursuing or have partially completed master's degrees, reflecting a strong commitment to professional growth. Teacher 1 (31, male, single) has been teaching outside his specialism for six years and was motivated by financial need and better job prospects in the city. Teacher 2 (28, male, single) has five years of experience and was influenced by job availability and his parents' preferences. Teacher 3 (27, female, single mother) has also taught outside her specialization for five years, primarily due to financial necessity and the availability of positions. Teacher 4 (40, female, married with three children) has 17 years of experience, with her assignment shaped by job requirements and a personal interest in the arts. Teacher 5 (32, female, single) has taught outside her field for ten years, driven by financial incentives and job availability.

Age and years of teaching experience significantly influence teachers' adaptability. Older and more experienced participants, like Teacher 4, demonstrate strong coping mechanisms and a deeper understanding of classroom dynamics, supporting Podolsky et al.'s (2019) assertion that experienced teachers develop broader instructional flexibility. Younger teachers, such as Teacher 3, often face more difficulties due to limited pedagogical experience. Gender also plays a role in coping strategies. Male participants (Teachers 1 and 2) frequently seek support from colleagues knowledgeable in the subjects they are teaching, finding this collaboration beneficial for instructional clarity. In contrast, female participants (Teachers 3, 4, and 5) tend to rely on self-learning through books, modules, and online platforms. This aligns with Doria and Ortega-Dela Cruz (2024), who found that men often benefit more from external support, while women employ more individual, self-directed coping strategies.

Educational attainment is another key factor. Teachers 1, 4, and 5 are pursuing or have completed graduate studies, which enhance their pedagogical skills and instructional methods. This supports Co et al. (2021) and Perez and Cruz (2024), who emphasized the role of advanced education in improving teacher competence and confidence. Meanwhile, Teachers 2 and 3, though holding only bachelor's degrees, demonstrate a strong willingness to develop professionally by using online resources and participating in seminars and training. According to Islam et al. (2017), such strategies are effective for teachers working outside their specialism, offering access to diverse materials and collaborative learning opportunities.

Civil status also influences teaching experiences. Teacher 4, the only married participant with children, benefits from her parenting experience when working with young learners. However, her family responsibilities limit her time for professional development. Similarly, Teacher 3, a single parent, faces time constraints that affect her ability to attend training. In contrast, single teachers like Teachers 1, 2, and 5 have greater flexibility to engage in seminars and workshops. This is consistent with Muwana and Chipindi's (2021) and Torres and Ortega-Dela Cruz (2022) findings that family obligations can hinder academic productivity and participation in professional growth activities.

These findings reflect key concepts from Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory. Older, more experienced teachers (e.g., Teachers 4 and 5) demonstrate a broader Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), allowing them to scaffold their own learning and effectively collaborate with peers. Teachers with higher educational attainment (Teachers 1, 4, and 5) utilize more advanced cultural tools and theoretical frameworks to manage the challenges of teaching outside their specialism. Gender differences influence coping strategies, with male participants relying on social support and females preferring self-directed learning. Civil status also impacts professional engagement, with single teachers having more time for growth opportunities, while those with family responsibilities face additional constraints. Overall, the demographic factors of the participants, shaped by their sociocultural contexts, play a crucial role in how they adapt, cope, and grow in teaching assignments beyond their area of expertise.

Lived Experiences of English Teachers Teaching Outside Specialism

This section explores the experiences of English teachers assigned to teach subjects outside their area of specialism, focusing on how these experiences shape their growth as educators. Using Self-Efficacy Theory as a framework—which posits that belief in one's ability to perform tasks significantly influences success—the analysis highlights how these teachers adapt, build resilience, and develop new competencies. It also demonstrates that teaching beyond one's specialization can foster valuable skills and perspectives, contributing to a more holistic and effective teaching practice.

The participants' experiences revealed three overarching themes: *Professional Mindset*, *Instructional Challenges*, and *Adaptive Strategies*. Under Professional Mindset, teachers expressed *strong dedication to their roles, driven by passion and a sense of responsibility*. Despite being assigned to unfamiliar subjects, they remained committed to student learning. Teacher 4, for example, acknowledged the difficulty of teaching primary-level subjects but found joy in her students' engagement.

"Yes, I find it hard to teach subjects, especially at the primary level, but I love seeing them learn. It makes me happy to see their activeness in the class discussion that makes me love more my job." (Teacher 4)

Similarly, Teacher 1 admitted that teaching outside his specialism was unexpected, yet he found fulfillment in inspiring learners.

"Even though this is not really what I expected when I applied to DepEd, I learned to enjoy the task given to me. It is enjoyable for me to inspire my learners to become achievers, plus their gratefulness in simple gestures is priceless." (Teacher 1)

Their experiences reflect the findings of Arendain and Limpot (2022), who noted that teachers often persist and thrive in unfamiliar teaching contexts due to a deep commitment to their profession.

Another key subtheme was *Confidence in Pedagogical Delivery*. Teachers emphasized that believing in their ability to deliver content—despite gaps in subject knowledge—played a crucial role in student engagement and learning. Teacher 4 admitted lacking training in early childhood education but gained confidence through hands-on experience. Teacher 5, though initially anxious about teaching mathematics, chose to deepen her understanding of the subject to ensure her learners met their required competencies.

“It is really a challenge for me to teach Kindergarten learners. Given that I have no experience during my undergraduate degree on how to teach these young learners, I do not hesitate to give my best. They are easy to teach because they are very young, and the lessons I teach to them make me even more confident.” (Teacher 4)

“Since I have a passion for kids, I am confident to face them. I was trained to face teenage learners, so when the time I was assigned to teach younger learners, it was not really a difficult task to do. Also, they are fun to handle because they appreciate the simple things I teach them.” (Teacher 5)

These examples align with Valencia et al. (2021), who found that self-confidence significantly enhances a teacher’s ability to manage the classroom, deliver lessons effectively, and address gaps in content knowledge.

Flexibility in Teaching Outside Specialism also emerged as a critical factor in overcoming instructional challenges. Participants shared how they adapted their teaching methods and embraced new roles with openness and creativity. Teacher 2 explained that his experiences with unexpected assignments helped him become more versatile and confident in adjusting to different teaching tasks. Teacher 3, who anticipated being assigned to subjects outside her specialism, found the experience particularly challenging in a public-school setting. However, with support from colleagues and prior private school experience, she discovered her capacity for flexibility.

“Working in DepEd taught me to be versatile. Until now, my principal has given me new tasks that are really beyond my expertise. That is why teaching other subjects is not new to me. I learned to be flexible, especially in teaching students. I can say that I can easily adjust to new lessons because of my experiences.” (Teacher 2)

“When I was deployed in my school, I already expected that I would handle subjects outside my specialism, it is not a surprise to me. Given my experiences in my private school, I learned different ways. However, it was way challenging in the public school where learners’ skills and intelligence are really behind their expected grade level. But my co-teachers helped me in many ways. I also discovered that I am flexible.” (Teacher 3)

These insights echo the study of Zaid et al. (2020), which emphasized that adaptability enhances teachers’ competence and classroom effectiveness, particularly when dealing with unfamiliar subjects.

Through their reflections, it became clear that flexibility is not just a survival skill but a catalyst for professional growth. It enables teachers to respond to varied learning needs, manage unexpected situations, and integrate diverse instructional strategies (Cardino & Cruz, 2020). This adaptability fosters continuous learning and enriches their teaching practice, benefiting both the educators and their students (Cruz, 2020; Ausa & Cruz, 2025). Ultimately, teaching outside one’s specialism can lead to increased confidence, broader pedagogical knowledge, and a deeper commitment to the teaching profession, affirming the value of resilience and flexibility in today’s dynamic educational landscape (Banal and Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2022).

Instructional Challenges

This theme highlights the difficulties English-major teachers face when teaching subjects outside their specialization. The challenges include mastering unfamiliar content, dealing with uncertainty and anxiety, and navigating language barriers.

One of the most significant issues is *content proficiency development*. Several participants expressed struggles with grasping the subject matter, requiring them to spend additional time preparing lessons. For example, Teacher 2 admitted difficulty teaching EPP due to limited knowledge in livelihood and industrial technology, contrasting it with the familiarity of English concepts. Despite this, he acknowledged that the experience allowed him to acquire valuable life skills.

“As someone who has limited knowledge about livelihood, agriculture, and industrial technology, it is really a challenge to me to teach EPP. In English, all I need to study is the concepts of words, grammar, and the like. But in EPP, the content that I need to study is rigorous. But I actually enjoy sometimes because I am also learning life skills.” (Teacher 2)

Similarly, Teacher 5 shared that teaching Grade 3 required her to adjust her instructional approach, as her training had been focused on older students.

“At first, my approach to students is for a higher level of thinking because that is what I was trained in during my college days. But it changed when I started teaching Grade 3. Aside from that, the content of the lessons that I need to prepare is easy yet challenging for me because I need to lower my approach since my students are primary levels.” (Teacher 5)

Both emphasized that subject mastery was essential, though challenging due to the steep learning curve and the need for intensive preparation.

Participants also reported *feelings of uncertainty and anxiety* when teaching unfamiliar subjects. Teacher 1 expressed self-doubt when teaching MAPEH, particularly Music, due to curriculum changes.

"I doubt myself sometimes about the correctness of my explanation in teaching MAPEH lessons, especially in Music. Yes, I know the basics since I learned it in grade school and high school but the lessons now in the new curriculum make me doubt myself." (Teacher 1)

Teacher 3 questioned her ability to teach Filipino effectively, despite being a language major, because the subject involved teaching in the learners' mother tongue.

"Although the lessons in Filipino 2 are easy, I question myself about the way I explain it to them. I am a language major, but teaching their mother tongue and the lessons keeps me wondering if I am teaching them effectively." (Teacher 3)

Teacher 5 shared her nervousness when a student asked a question about adding decimals—highlighting how unfamiliarity with specific rules can trigger anxiety.

"There was one time during our Mathematics time when a bright student asked about adding decimals, I immediately doubted myself because, in the first place, adding decimals has different rules. But I was able to answer him. It is really nerve-wracking, Sir, that there might be students asking something I really do not know." (Teacher 5)

These feelings reflect the findings of Anselmo and Anselmo (2024), who noted that teachers new to a subject often experience inadequacy. Similarly, Cruz (2016), Buenacosa and Petalla (2022) linked reduced self-efficacy to gaps in subject knowledge, reinforcing how uncertainty can affect performance and confidence in the classroom.

Another recurring challenge was *variation in language use*. Switching between English and Filipino as the medium of instruction posed communication difficulties for several participants. Teacher 2 admitted feeling more confident in English but often doubted his use of Filipino technical terms in EPP.

"When in English, I feel more confident, but when I need to teach EPP, which is taught in Filipino, I sometimes worry about whether I am using the right terms." (Teacher 2)

Teacher 1, despite being multilingual, found it challenging to explain concepts in Filipino, particularly when unfamiliar with certain terms.

"From someone who knows three languages, it is challenging for me to teach in Filipino since this is not my mother tongue. Switching from English to Filipino in explaining the lesson poses a challenge to me because, at times, there are technical terms in Filipino that I really do not understand, so I have to consult my colleagues." (Teacher 1)

Teacher 5 shared how switching languages sometimes disrupted her ability to effectively communicate lessons.

"The medium of instruction changes how I communicate the content. Sometimes I get lost in transition, and I am not sure if the students are really getting the idea. I had to learn how to be more patient and find simpler ways to explain things in Filipino." (Teacher 5)

These insights align with Tupas and Martin (2016) and Dangan and Cruz (2021), who emphasized the emotional and cognitive demands of bilingual instruction. Teachers often face a mismatch between language proficiency and subject matter, which can hinder clarity and affect both teaching and student learning outcomes.

Adaptive Strategies and Opportunities

Despite the challenges they face teaching outside their specialism, participants developed effective strategies to manage their classrooms and deliver instruction. A key approach is *learner-centered instruction*, where teachers adapt their methods to meet diverse learner needs and evolving curriculum requirements. Teacher 2 emphasized the necessity of using varied strategies due to the different learning styles of students in public schools, while Teacher 1 reflected on how the complex MATATAG curriculum pushed him to reconsider his lesson delivery, ensuring it aligns with how his learners engage with content.

"Learners nowadays in public school are hard to teach, adding up the new curriculum set by the DepEd. In fact, in every lesson, I need to have a different approach because I have noticed that they have varied ways of learning, and it solely depends on good instruction." (Teacher 2)

"In Grade 4, the MATATAG Curriculum is a bit complex for me. The challenge to teach a subject I have not fully mastered is a challenge, yet MATATAG also caused me to reflect on the way I deliver my lesson. I do not want to see it as a burden, but the way I explain the lessons is different based on how my learners approach learning." (Teacher 1)

These adaptations mirror Serdyukov's (2017), Cruz's (2020), Cardino and Cruz's (2020) advocacy for flexible learning environments that accommodate individual learner differences. Similarly, Doria and Ortega-Dela Cruz (2024), and Davis et al. (2024), Ramoso and Cruz (2024) highlighted adaptability as a vital skill that develops through ongoing reflection and directly impacts classroom management and teacher well-being. By modifying their instruction, these teachers ensure effective learning despite teaching subjects outside their expertise.

Managing diverse classrooms also demanded *diverse classroom management* skills. Participants described efforts to engage students with varying abilities and backgrounds, including those with special needs. Teacher 4 shared the challenge of balancing the needs of both regular students and those with disabilities under DepEd's inclusive education policies, despite lacking specific training for the latter.

"...I have four students who have been diagnosed with special needs, and I am not trained to handle them. In the new memorandum released by DepEd, they emphasized that inclusion should be maintained inside the classroom. Since I am handling young learners, it really takes a toll on me to devise teaching strategies to both cater to the regular students and those with special needs." (Teacher 4)

Teacher 3 recounted initial shock when encountering learners with learning disabilities but noted gradual improvement through professional development.

"...you know, teaching other subjects I do not major is a challenge accepted, but being faced by learners with learning disability is a whole new level. I was shocked the first time I encountered such, but with the help of the training slowly, I have been adjusting my teaching style." (Teacher 3)

These experiences align with Adewumi et al. (2017), Cardino and Cruz (2020) who argue that teachers must be equipped not only to maintain order but also to effectively support diverse learners in mastering complex material. Anselmo and Anselmo (2024) further emphasize that tailoring approaches to students with special needs, along with parental support, reduces stress and improves learning outcomes. This highlights how resilience and ongoing learning enable teachers to create inclusive environments, even when working outside their specialization.

Interestingly, some teachers found *positive aspects in teaching less complex subjects*. They appreciated that lighter subjects allowed more focus on pedagogy rather than heavy content preparation. Teacher 3 noted the relief in teaching EPP compared to the demands of English, where extensive data collection and lesson preparation are required.

"As the English Coordinator, I prepare monthly reports. Another one is that English is a major subject, thus requiring a lot of data from learners and teachers, from reading to competencies and a lot more. Compared to teaching EPP, I find it more convenient for me because, firstly, it is not a major subject, and also, the lessons are less complex and can easily be taught." (Teacher 3)

Teacher 2 valued the reduced pressure, which enabled a deeper connection with students and more enjoyable learning experiences.

"Since the subject I was assigned is not too heavy, I do not feel as pressured as I would in my major subject. This gives me the chance to really connect with my students and make learning more enjoyable." (Teacher 2)

These views are supported by research such as Rahayu and Osman (2019), Cruz (2020, and Torres and Ortega-Dela Cruz (2024), who link manageable curricula to enhanced teaching effectiveness and engagement, and Murati (2015), who observed that reduced content demands foster more interactive instruction. Blömeke et al. (2016), Ramoso and Cruz (2024) further argue that teacher well-being and satisfaction significantly influence classroom effectiveness; thus, lighter teaching loads can boost motivation and instructional quality.

These adaptive strategies and reflections resonate strongly with *Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory*, which asserts that belief in one's capability fundamentally shapes motivation and behavior. Teachers' struggles with unfamiliar content, like Teacher 2's challenges with EPP, illustrate how gaps in mastery can undermine confidence and willingness to engage fully. Conversely, observation and support from colleagues play a crucial role in enhancing self-efficacy. For instance, Teacher 1's reliance on peer consultations to clarify technical terms underscores the value of collaborative professional learning communities where teachers share strategies and bolster each other's confidence. Emotional challenges such as anxiety and self-doubt, exemplified by Teacher 5's nervousness during a math lesson, further impact instructional effectiveness. Addressing these through mentoring, formative feedback, and targeted professional development fosters emotional resilience and improves both teacher confidence and student outcomes (Banal and Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2022). Thus, systemic support is essential to empower teachers working outside their specialism to succeed and thrive in their roles.

4. Conclusions

This study examined the lived experiences of English teachers assigned to teach outside their specialism. Despite facing challenges with unfamiliar content, teachers demonstrated strong professional commitment, driven by passion, responsibility, and adaptability. Confidence in pedagogy and instructional flexibility emerged as critical factors in maintaining student engagement and classroom effectiveness, even in the absence of subject-matter expertise. Demographic differences shaped teacher experiences. Older teachers drew on their professional maturity, while younger ones faced steeper learning curves. Male teachers often relied on peer support and professional development, whereas female teachers showed strong self-reliance, utilizing digital tools and personal initiative. Those with advanced degrees actively pursued growth opportunities, while less formally trained teachers expressed interest in further development. The findings underscore the evolving nature of teaching roles and highlight a broader systemic challenge—the need to support out-of-field teachers to ensure instructional quality. While these educators face significant obstacles, their resilience, adaptability, and dedication allow them to persist and succeed.

This study offers practical implications for educators, school leaders, and policymakers, advocating for sustained support through mentorship, collaboration, and targeted professional development. Addressing these needs is essential for advancing educational equity and quality, especially in under-resourced contexts. Future research should investigate the long-term impact of out-of-field teaching on student outcomes and teacher well-being. Comparative and longitudinal studies across different contexts can provide deeper insight into how teachers navigate, adapt to, and grow within these assignments—informing more responsive and equitable teacher deployment policies.

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Author Contribution Statement

First Author (DOTC): Literature review, conceptualization, methodology, data analysis, original manuscript preparation

Second/Corresponding Author (RAOD): review-editing and writing, journal article preparation.

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